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Research Article

IMPLEMENTATION OF VASCULAR ENDOTHELIAL GROWTH FACTOR IN PERIODONTAL DISEASES TREATMENT

V.P. Mudrov^{1,2}, V.N. Nelyubin³, I.S. Fomenkov⁴, S.Y. Ivanov⁴

V.P. Mudrov PhD, Department of immunology "Russian medical Academy continuous professional education" Ministry of Healthcare of Russia; doctor of clinical laboratory diagnostics FSBI "9 diagnostic and treatment center" Ministry of Defense of Russia, Moscow, Russia

V.N. Nelyubin MD, leading researcher FSBEI "Moscow State University of Medicine and Dentistry A.I. Yevdokimov" of the Ministry of Healthcare of the Russia, Moscow, Russia;

I.S. Fomenkov FSBEI First Moscow state medical University I. M. Sechenov of Ministry of Healthcare of Russia, Moscow, Russia;

S.Y. Ivanov MD, Professor, corresponding member of the RAS head of the Department of maxillofacial surgery, FSBEI First Moscow state medical University I. M. Sechenov of Ministry of Healthcare, Moscow, Russia;

¹FSBEI PGE "Russian medical Academy continuous professional education" Ministry of Healthcare of Russia, Moscow, Russia;

²FSBI "9 diagnostic and treatment center" Ministry of Defense of Russia, Moscow, Russia;

³FSBEI of the Higher Education "Moscow State University of Medicine and Dentistry A.I. Yevdokimov" of the Ministry of Healthcare of the Russian Federation, Moscow, Russia;

⁴FSBEI First Moscow state medical University named after I. M. Sechenov of Ministry of Healthcare of Russia, Moscow, Russia;

Abstract:

Periodontal diseases, including gingivitis and periodontitis are often associated with progressive loss of periodontal bone and soft tissue. Studies highlight the effectiveness of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) use in periodontitis therapy as it stimulates microvascular perfusion improvement and contributes to connective and bone tissue regeneration.

Ten patients at the age 53-79 with diagnosed periodontitis were examined and treated in the department of oral and maxillofacial surgery UKH №4. Besides standard drug therapy, treatment also included VEGF gel which represents a composition of bioresorbable carbohydrates on the basis of carboxymethylcellulose, forming the cellular basis for similar extracellular matrix.

Immunohistochemical methods showed a decrease in extracellular secretion of VEGF, as well as the construction of fibers not only from "young" collagen type III, but also collagen type I. Thus, not only stimulation of regeneration was noted, but also a pronounced anti-inflammatory effect of hydrogel with a vascular endothelial growth factor having the potential to stimulate regeneration of periodontal tissues.

Key words: *periodontal microflora, interferon γ , vascular endothelial growth factor, type I collagen*

Corresponding author:**I.S. Fomenkov,**

117638, Moscow, Elektrolitniy proezd 16/7, flat 91

Email: Dr-fomenkov@yandex.ru

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Periodontal diseases, including gingivitis and periodontitis, are the most common diseases of oral cavity with prevalence about 90% of world population. [4] They are often associated with progressive loss of periodontal bone and soft tissue. The balance between maintaining periodontal health and beginning of periodontal destruction reflects the ongoing struggle between the vast oral microbiota and the array of resident and emigrating periodontal immune cells. [1, 2]

Due to high virulence of pathogenic microorganisms new methods of treatment are being investigated. One of such methods is related to possible improvement of periodontal microcirculation which stimulates tissue immunity and microbial biofilm destruction. [5,6] Studies highlight the effectiveness of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) use in periodontitis therapy as it stimulates microvascular perfusion improvement and contributes to connective and bone tissue regeneration. [3,6]

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Ten patients at the age 53-79 with diagnosed periodontitis were examined and treated in the department of oral and maxillofacial surgery UCH №4. Besides standard drug therapy, treatment also included VEGF gel which represents a composition of bioresorbable carbohydrates on the basis of carboxymethylcellulose, forming the cellular basis for similar extracellular matrix. In the course of study VEGF, IFN- γ and pathogenic microflora of periodontal were examined in a sample of dentogingival fluid; histological and immunohistochemical research was conducted.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

As a result of treatment, the concentration of pathogenic microflora of periodontium was significantly reduced: *A. actinomycetomcomitans*, *P. endodontalis*, *P. intermedia*, *T. denticola*, *T. forsythia* и *F. nucleatum*. The concentration of VEGF in the periodontal pocket decreased after the treatment and normal histoarchitectonics of the gingival mucosa was found.

Immunohistochemical methods showed a decrease in extracellular secretion of VEGF, as well as the construction of fibers not only from "young" collagen type III, but also collagen type I. This indicates a decrease in the activity of inflammation and activation of the plastic processes of the fibrous component, leading to the strengthening of the periodontal structures on the background of the treatment.

Thus, not only stimulation of regeneration was noted, but also a pronounced anti-inflammatory

effect of hydrogel with a vascular endothelial growth factor having the potential to stimulate regeneration of periodontal tissues.

CONCLUSION:

Implementation of VEGF in traditional complex treatment of periodontitis increases therapy effectiveness, accelerates epithelialization, stimulates activation of regeneration potential of periodontal tissue and has a pronounced anti-inflammatory effect.

Abbreviations

1. VEGF - vascular endothelial growth factor
2. UCH – university clinical hospital

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